

ENHANCING FINANCIAL ALLOCATION PRACTICES IN A PUBLICLY OWNED WATER UTILITY: A FRAMEWORK FOR EFFECTIVE BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION

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ABSTRACT

This study examined financial allocation practices in Publicly-Owned Water Utilities (POWUs) through the lens of key stakeholders' experiences. Using in-depth interviews at a specific POWU in the Philippines, the research explored challenges like limited resources and competing priorities, while also identifying opportunities for improvement. Thematic analysis revealed the importance of stakeholder engagement and data-driven planning. Based on these findings, a framework was developed for POWUs that incorporates multi-criteria decision-making, social impact assessment, transparency, and data-driven planning with risk management. This framework aims to empower POWUs to make informed financial decisions that ensure both long-term financial stability and high-quality water service delivery.

Keywords: *financial allocation, publicly-owned water utilities, resource allocation, business administration principles*

INTRODUCTION

Publicly-Owned Water Utilities (POWUs) play a vital role in ensuring public health by providing safe and reliable water access. However, effectively allocating resources within POWUs remains a significant challenge (World Bank, 2016). Factors like low water tariffs, non-revenue water losses, and economic downturns often force POWUs to prioritize immediate needs over long-term investments (Grafton et al., 2018). This can

lead to a trade-off between essential maintenance and infrastructure upgrades, potentially jeopardizing future sustainability and service quality.

Despite the critical nature of resource allocation for POWU success, a gap exists in research that explores the lived experiences of stakeholders involved in these financial decisions. Understanding these experiences can provide valuable insights into how POWUs prioritize resource allocation and the potential impact on long-term financial health.

This study addresses this gap by focusing on Company X, a POWU in Laguna, Philippines. Through in-depth interviews with key stakeholders, the research investigates the formulation and execution of financial policies within Company X. By analyzing these experiences, the study aims to identify how resources are distributed across various water utility activities, determine if resource allocation aligns with activities that generate the most value and contribute to long-term financial health, gain insights into the decision-making processes and priorities used by personnel in authority.

This research holds significant value as it explored into the practicalities of financial allocation within POWUs. By understanding the challenges and opportunities faced by Company X, the study aims to contribute to the development of improved resource allocation practices for POWUs globally.

Research Questions

In this study, the financial allocation practices in Company X were studied by using the following research questions:

1. What are the experiences of key stakeholders on the formulation and execution of financial policies in the selected publicly-owned water utility?
2. What are the perspectives of the key stakeholders in their engagement and participation in the formulation and execution of financial policies influencing financial allocation decisions on business objectives?
3. What business administration principles framework can be adapted to improve the financial allocation practices in the water utility context?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The qualitative investigation into participants' formulation and execution of financial policies influencing financial allocation decisions on business objectives formed the basis for this study's assumptions and findings. Utilizing a phenomenological approach, this research aimed to better understand the phenomenon under investigation. According to Creswell (2013), qualitative research develops assumptions and applies interpretative and theoretical frameworks to explore the meanings individuals or groups attach to social

or human situations. The purpose of this paper was to provide additional insights into a specific characteristic related to a particular field of inquiry.

Research Locale

The selection of Company X, as a POWU serving over 70,000 connections in Laguna, Philippines, offers a strategically significant case study. This choice aligns with the research objective of examining financial allocation practices in local water district scale. Company X's substantial footprint within Laguna's water infrastructure, coupled with documented financial constraints and infrastructure challenges, presents a compelling opportunity for analysis. These challenges, including limited funding and service disruptions, directly impact the utility's ability to fulfill its critical role.

Research Participants

The total research participants of the study were composed of four (4) top management employees from different departments in the company. They were the key stakeholders in their respective departments. Two (2) of them came from the administrative and finance sections while the two (2) others were from the technical services and operations management. All participants were selected homogenously in one locale.

Research Instruments

The semi-structured interview guide questions were used in this study. The participants were asked an identical set of questions relative to the participants' lived experiences related to the financial allocation practices in the POWU. The researcher conducted the interview based on the scripted interview guide questions. The interview guide consisted of twelve questions subjected to expert validation. The content of the questions focused on the lived experiences in the formulation and execution of financial policies influencing financial allocation decisions on business objectives of the company.

Data Gathering Procedure

The interview employed a verified instrument guide. Before data collecting, the researcher obtained interview materials. Key stakeholders were interviewed using an interview guide. The researcher established rapport with the subject and performed the interview at the individual's request through an appointment.

Data Construction

Data analysis involves the systematic search and arrangement of interview transcripts, observation notes, and other non-textual resources in qualitative research. The data analysis (Thematic Analysis) based on Creswell (2014) aims to identify themes from lived experiences of the key stakeholders. Raw interview data was transcribed to prepare it for analysis. The researcher read all data for data coding and identified themes after data coding. The final data (thematic) analysis analyzed related themes' meanings. These

interpretations and understandings were used to build a business administration principles framework.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. *Experiences on the Formulation and Execution of Financial*

The analysis of interview data yielded a variety of themes related to financial allocation in the organization. For deeper exploration, themes were regrouped into three distinct clusters, such as: Decision-making to examine how resource allocation decisions are made and the processes involved; Resource allocation to know how resources are distributed and managed for projects in the POWU; and Organizational effectiveness to analyze the impact of financial allocation practices on business overall effectiveness. Themes in these clusters considered financial sustainability, community impact, and efficient resource utilization.

Table 1. Themes and sub-themes of Key Stakeholders' Experiences

Themes	Sub-themes
A. Decision-Making	
1. Financial Planning	i. Risk Mitigation
	ii. Forecasting
B. Resource Allocation	
1. Cost Optimization	i. Manual Processing
2. Technological Integration	ii. Cost Reduction Strategies
C. Organizational Effectiveness	
1. Accountability & Transparency	
2. Financial Management	
3. External Influences	

Several key themes related to decision-making, resource allocation, and organizational effectiveness. Stakeholders faced significant challenges in financial decision-making, particularly in accurately forecasting water demand and infrastructure needs due to factors such as population growth and climate change. This aligns with Brown and Johnson's (2021) emphasis on the necessity of sophisticated forecasting models and continuous data analysis. Additionally, the complexity of evolving water treatment technologies and fluctuating construction costs highlighted the need for ongoing market research and expert knowledge, as underscored by Rajendran (2023).

Resource allocation emerged as another critical area, with stakeholders identifying inefficiencies in manual processes and advocating for automation to improve efficiency and reduce costs, a trend supported by Almeida et al. (2021). Furthermore, stakeholders stressed the importance of accountability and transparency in financial practices to maintain public trust, reflecting principles of good governance highlighted by Un-Water

(2022). Organizational effectiveness was also a major concern, with stakeholders navigating challenges such as limited financial resources, political pressures, regulatory impacts, and data limitations. For example, investments in new water treatment plants due to stricter environmental regulations necessitated stakeholder engagement for insights on cost forecasting, market analysis, and contingency fund allocation, in line with David and Abaño's (2019) recommendations.

The findings from the experiences underscored the complex balancing act required for effective financial allocation within POWUs. Stakeholders emphasized the need for long-term planning, responsible resource allocation, and a focus on environmental sustainability. By prioritizing strategic planning, transparency, and technological integration, policymakers can enhance long-term financial health, ensure efficient resource management, and contribute to a more sustainable water future. Integrating stakeholder perspectives, as suggested by Almeida et al. (2021), can significantly improve decision-making processes, leading to more resilient and sustainable financial practices.

2. Perspectives on Engagement and Participation Influencing Financial Allocation

Table 2 shows the themes and subthemes that emerged from the participants' perspectives on the engagement and participation influencing financial allocation decisions on business objectives.

Table 2. Themes and sub-themes of Key Stakeholders' Perspectives

Themes	Sub-themes
A. Decision-Making	
1. Financial Planning Challenges	i. Forecasting Needs ii. Market Analysis
B. Resource Allocation	
1. Infrastructure Development	i. Budget Buffering
2. Strategic Investment	
3. Project Management Challenges	
C. Organizational Effectiveness	
1. Unforeseen Expenses	
2. Community Impact	i. Customer Service
3. Future Sustainability	i. Long-term Plans

Examining the financial allocation practices as viewed by the participants at Company X identified challenges that mirror those faced by other utilities. The key stakeholders reported difficulties in financial planning, forecasting needs, and market analysis. Predicting water demand and infrastructure needs is complicated by factors such as population growth and climate change, necessitating flexible plans and thorough data analysis.

In resource allocation, stakeholders also emphasized the importance of reserving funds for unexpected maintenance focus on long-term infrastructure health. Investments in water conservation and renewable energy were deemed essential for sustainability, reflecting trends noted by Almeida et al. (2021). Effective project management requires strong planning and accurate cost estimates to avoid budget overruns, underscoring Rajendran's (2023) emphasis on robust project methodologies.

The need for financial resilience and balancing customer service with cost control, echoing views on risk management and focus on customer-centric approaches. Open communication with the community regarding financial decisions was seen as crucial, reflecting the importance of transparency. For future sustainability, stakeholders advocated for plans that consider future environmental regulations and technological advancements. This aligns with the call for integrating sustainability into financial planning as stakeholder engagement is vital for informed decisions about technology investments, savings, and achieving sustainability goals.

The themes found in the perspectives of the research participants confirms the importance of existing knowledge on the topic. Adaptable planning, strategic resource allocation, robust project management, and stakeholder engagement are vital for long-term financial health, efficient service delivery, and a sustainable water future.

3. Framework For Effective Business Administration

POWUs operate uniquely compared to for-profit organizations, focusing on providing safe and reliable water services at affordable rates while adhering to strict regulations and ensuring financial sustainability (Larsen et al., 2021). Unlike profit-driven businesses prioritizing shareholder returns, POWUs emphasize public health and well-being (Brown & Johnson, 2021). This requires adapting business administration principles to balance competing priorities, regulatory compliance, and financial sustainability.

Figure 1. Proposed Framework for Effective Business Administration

A proposed framework based on participant experiences and perspectives addresses these needs with three key components: Sustainable Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM), Transparency and Stakeholder Engagement, and Data-Driven Planning and Risk Management. MCDM integrates social and environmental impacts into financial decisions, ensuring balanced outcomes (Radmehr et al., 2022).

Transparency and Stakeholder Engagement build trust through open communication and stakeholder participation (Akhmouch & Clavreul, 2016). Data-Driven Planning uses financial modeling and analytics to optimize resource allocation and efficiency. Integrating these components can empower the POWU to make informed decisions for financial sustainability, efficient service delivery, and responsible environmental stewardship, promoting sustainable water management for the community. This framework is effective for POWU business administration because it balances traditional financial considerations with social and environmental impact assessments, ensuring responsible decision-making that prioritizes both public well-being and long-term financial health.

Conclusions

This study explored the key stakeholders' lived experiences and perspectives in Company X in terms of its own formulation and execution of financial allocation practices. The findings of this study were used as a basis to propose a framework for improving financial allocation practices in the water utility context. The study concluded that:

1. Stakeholders highlighted the significant impact of the formulation and execution of financial policies on financial decision-making in the POWU context. This underscores the challenge of finding a balance between these policies and the current financial allocation management approaches. POWUs need to navigate this complex landscape to ensure effective financial management.
2. Stakeholders stressed the significance of long-term infrastructure investments, precise forecasting of future demands, and improved cooperation in financial planning. This emphasizes the necessity for Company X to embrace a long-term strategic goal that thoughtfully strikes a balance between long-term sustainability and customer service. The capacity to accomplish business objectives and maintain long-term financial health depends heavily on strategic investments, market analysis, and budget buffer building. This reinforces the need for a long-term strategic plan that balances long-term sustainability with customer service. Strategic investments, coupled with market analysis and building budget buffers, are crucial for achieving business objectives while ensuring long-term financial health.
3. Company X had been offered a framework for effective business administration principles. This framework identifies three essential components to support well-informed financial decisions that take social, environmental, and financial objectives into account. The integration of social and environmental factors, the promotion of transparency and stakeholder engagement, the use of long-term

financial modeling in conjunction with scenario planning and risk management, the conduct of life-cycle cost analysis with sustainability considerations, and the utilization of data-driven decision support for operational efficiency are some of these components. A POWU can improve their budget allocation procedures and support long-term sustainability and effective service delivery in their distinct public service purpose by putting these concepts into practice. This framework outlines three key components to guide well-informed financial decisions that encompass social, environmental, and financial goals.

Recommendations

By applying the findings from this study, water utilities like Company X and other publicly-owned water utilities (POWUs) can gain valuable insights and benefit in the long term. This can help communities and the environment by laying the groundwork for improved financial practices. The study offers the following recommendations:

1. Ensure that diverse stakeholders are included in financial decision-making, and regularly evaluate and improve these strategies to incorporate stakeholders' perspectives effectively.
2. Equip top management with skills in risk identification, assessment, and mitigation to support proactive and future-proof financial decision-making.
3. Create comprehensive strategies for integrating sustainability considerations into financial planning and decision-making.
4. Implement key performance indicators (KPIs) to track the effectiveness and efficiency of financial allocation practices. Conduct regular reviews and audits to identify areas for improvement and ensure compliance with regulations and best practices.
5. Foster a culture where stakeholders and staff can provide feedback and suggest adaptations to the financial framework, ensuring ongoing optimization for future needs and challenges.

To achieve a more comprehensive understanding of efficient service delivery, future research should incorporate the perspectives of POWU consumers and users through a mixed-method approach. Combining quantitative surveys for broad insights with qualitative interviews for a richer understanding of user experiences can provide valuable data for developing efficient and user-centered service delivery practices within POWUs.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research prioritized ethical principles throughout. Prior approvals were obtained, and participation was voluntary. The design minimized harm and ensured confidentiality through pseudonyms and secure data storage. Proper citations prevented plagiarism,

and objectivity was maintained through formal communication. Data, files, and documentation were meticulously compiled to support the research. Additionally, trust with participants was fostered, data anonymity was ensured, and potential biases were acknowledged and mitigated. Rigorous validation strategies like triangulation and member checking further strengthened the ethical framework.

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REFERENCES

- Akhmouch, A., & Clavreul, D. (2016). Stakeholder engagement for inclusive water governance: "Practicing What We Preach" with the OECD Water Governance Initiative. *Water*, 8(5), 204. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w8050204>
- Almeida, M. C., Brito, R. S., Jorge, C., & Cardoso, M. A. (2021). Performance assessment system to wastewater utilities strategic planning. *Water*, 13(18), 2489. Located in <https://doi.org/10.3390/w13182489>
- Brown, J., & Johnson, R. (2021). Strategic workforce planning for water utilities: A practical guide. American Water Works Association.
- Creswell, J. W. (2013) Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research. (4th ed.). Boston, MA: Pearson.
- David, S. D., Jr., & Abaño, S. P. (2019). Water resources in the Philippines: Status, challenges and opportunities. SCPW. Retrieved from <https://wetlands.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/03>
- Department of Budget and Management. (2022). National budget memorandum no. 143 dated April 28, 2022. <https://www.dbm.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/Issuances/2022/national-budget-memorandum-no-143-dated-april-28-2022.pdf>
- Grafton, R. Q., Wyrwoll, S. A., Wheeler, S. A., & Peterson, J. M. (2018). Global insights into water resources, climate change and governance. *Nature Climate Change*, 8(11), 941-945.
- Larsen, K., Guhathakurta, S., & Haas, P. (2021). Financial sustainability of public water utilities in the United States: A benchmarking study. RAND Corporation.

- Local Water Utilities Administration Act, 1973 [Republic Act No. 6849]. (n.d.). Retrieved March 08, 2024, from <https://legislature.maine.gov/statutes/35-A/title35-Ach64.pdf>
- National Water Resources Board. (n.d.). About Us. Retrieved April 23, 2024, from <https://nwrwb.gov.ph/>
- Radmehr, A., Bozorg-Haddad, O., & Loáiciga, H. A. (2022). Integrated strategic planning and multi-criteria decision-making framework with its application to agricultural water management. *Scientific Reports*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-12194-5>
- Rajendran, K. (2023). Comparing public administration and business administration: Understanding key differences and similarities. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/comparing-public-administration-business-key-karthik-rajendran/>
- Un-Water (2022). Progress on integrated water resources management – 2021 update UN-Water. Retrieved from <https://www.unwater.org/publications/progress-integrated-water-resources-management-2021-update>
- World Bank. (2016). *The state of the water sector*. Washington, DC: World Bank